

STYLISTIC, LEXICAL SEMANTIC AND STRUCTURAL GRAMMATICAL ANALYSIS OF ZOONYM-COMPONENT PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13934716>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 05- Oktyabr 2024 yil
 Ma'qullandi: 10- Oktyabr 2024 yil
 Nashr qilindi: 15- Oktyabr 2024 yil

KEYWORDS

zoonyms, idioms, phraseological units, lexicology, Uzbek and English languages, proverbs, metaphor.

ABSTRACT

in this article, the author analyses the lexical differences of zoonym-component phraseological units in Uzbek and English. Defining zoonyms as a semantic group in lexicology will be the main topic of this research. And the writer of this article compares some Uzbek and English idioms or some zoonym-included phrases how likely both languages` association with zoonyms in these languages.

The first thing we need to learn is what a zoonym is. Zoonym consists of two parts: zoonym, which means names of animals used in languages. The term zoonym could be used in science and literature variously. Additionally, zoonym components are described as an animal name, while we use them as a part of speech in everyday conversations to refer to human characters sometimes.

There can be listed so many idioms and phrases, including animal names in both languages. As an example, an English idiom - crow doesn't pick crow's eyes - will be analysed as follows. Here, as a literal meaning it is defined that There is an understanding between people who belong to the same group so they don't harm one another. The first word "crow" is used as a subject and the next one is as an object of the idiom.

As well as this, if we look into the meaning and position of the phrase "... crow's eyes" more deeply, the second word "crow" is a dependent word "eyes" and "eyes" is the dependent word in this phrase.

Having said that, in Uzbek this idiom has right its own xerox - "qarg'a qarg'ani ko'zini cho'qimaydi". Likely, in both languages zoonyms serve as the same part of speech and meaning. One more sample to learn is "two dogs over one bone seldom agree". This is translated slightly different in Uzbek - "ikki qo'chqor kallasi bir qozonda qaynamaydi". The definition of the English version is obvious, meanwhile in Uzbek it is interpreted as 'two heads never boiled in the same pan'. A sense of meaning, two the same-characterised-people never see eye to eye with one another. In English, the word "dog" comes as a subject in this statement. However, Uzbek idiom uses the head of the dog as an independent word and dog is a dependent word in which both of the words make up one subject joining each other. Semantically, both of the animals cannot get on well with each other due to their characters.

Some other examples of phrases in English: somebody kills two birds with one stone, cry wolf, the dog barks, but the caravan goes on.

To conclude, in this chapter of the both irrelevant languages, zoonyms are discussed on a grammar basis and this will have a great impact on leaning the diversity between grammar and the phraseological units of Uzbek and English.

Animals and people have been residing interacting with each other for a long ancient time in social life and other walks of life. Animals have always played a significant role not only in practical jobs people do, but in the world of languages. Words, phrases, proverbs, idioms, metaphorical phrases in languages related to zoonym are discussed in a huge demand, particularly in lexicology, structural grammar, and in stylistics. Animal names are used in many fields of science - in biology, zoology, literature or in mother tongues. In the following parts, we shall learn how zoonyms are used lexicologically, grammatically and stylistically.

In lexicology words are defined in monosemantic and polysemantic ways in terms of their meaning. In Uzbek and English, generally the names of animals are usually named after their characters, habits, residential areas, their colours and shapes. Polar bears, for instance, are vertebrate-animals which live in the North Pole and its colour is in white. Comparing this animal to Uzbek, there can be seen no change in naming them. In Uzbek, " oq ayiq yoki qutb ayig'i - bu umurtqali hayvon bo'lib, Shimoliy Qutb yerlarida istiqomad qiladi". As we can see in both definitions, place names are added in the word bear. Even though these languages are totally unrelated to each other, calling the names of most animals makes no difference.

However, on the other hand zoonyms are expressed literally, which sometimes mean positively, sometimes in a negative sense in both languages. Moreover, some zoonym phrases include names of the animals according to the cultural diversity. One sample of English idiom: "... when pigs fly" seem to be unrealistic when it is translated word by word and it is impossible for pigs to fly, so when someone says this, they are saying that something will (most likely) never happen. By contrast, in Uzbek language there is an equivalent of this idiomatic phrase - "... tuyani dumi yerga tekkanda (English translation is 'when tail of camel reaches down to ground)". Translating into any language, it is crystal-clear that its tale never comes down to the ground. So, it means - as the same as the English idiom - that something is never likely to happen. This could be comprehended by its drift meaning. When it comes to choice of the animals in these idioms, both nations have used those animals as a pet culturally. This may be concluded lexically that any native speaker takes a zoonym originating from their way of life.

Both languages compose some interesting metaphorical phrases or idioms. In this sense, phrases mostly portray situations or character of people literally. Animal characters are matched to humans' in different ways. In Uzbek language sheep is considered a gentle domestic animal and usually it is seen as not a mischief animal among other pets. "... qo'y og'zidan cho'p olmagan kishi yoki odam (in English definition: someone who has never taken away any litter from the mouth of a sheep)". This means somebody who is so gentle in Uzbek ideology. In comparison to English, this idiom can meet its replica. " A pussy cat" is someone who is very gentle and never hurt anyone. In these phrases cat and sheep are metaphorical phrases that show similarity between animal and human personality and equally they are common pets among Uzbek and English everyday life.

In conclusion, while learning zoonyms in these languages will probably create an immense opportunity to open a new corridor in languages, analysing idioms, proverbs, and other phraseological units in lexicology.

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